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IDENTIFICATION OF DEPRESSED ADOLESCENTS:
DEPRESSION SCREENING EDUCATION FOR SCHOOL NURSES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

One third of American teenagers suffer from depression. However, less than half of them receive the treatment they need. Untreated depression is often associated with absenteeism, poor academic performance, behavioral, and social problems. It can also increase risk of violence, alcohol or drug abuse, and even suicide. The American Academy of Pediatrics and the U.S. Preventive Service Task Force both recommend routine screening of adolescents for depression. However, screening rates in ambulatory settings are very low. School nurses, often the first health care professionals to encounter these young people, are well-positioned to recognize depression and make referrals to medical and mental health providers for proper diagnosis, referral, and treatment. Despite their access to teens, many school nurses do not feel confident addressing depression and are not comfortable in using a standardized screening tool. Using the PRECEDE framework for health program planning, barriers preventing school nurses from depression screening were identified. To remove some of these barriers, an education module was developed to provide training for school nurses on adolescent depression and screening. This education module is easily accessible online. It consists of a video presentation on adolescent depression, the PHQ-9 screening tool, and a case study. It also provides links to online resources and the PHQ-9 screening and referral forms. It is anticipated that after completion of the training, school nurses will have increased knowledge and confidence in identification and referral of the students at risk.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF FIGURES	vi
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	vii
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Purpose of the Project.....	4
Conceptual Framework.....	4
Phase One – Social Assessment.....	6
Phase Two – Epidemiological Assessment	6
Phase Three – Behavioral and Environmental Assessment.....	7
Phase Four – Educational and Ecological Assessment.....	7
Phase Five – Administrative and Policy Assessment.....	8
Phase Six – Implementation	9
Phases Seven through Nine – Process, Impact, and Outcome Evaluation	9
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	10
Search Method.....	10
The Importance of Adolescent Depression Screening in Schools.....	11
Providers’ Attitudes, Perceptions, and Beliefs in Adolescent Depression Screening.....	12
Depression Screening Tool for Adolescent in the School Setting.....	13
PROJECT GOALS & OBJECTIVES.....	15
METHODS	16
Target Population and Setting.....	16
Ethical Consideration.....	16
Content Research	16
Education Module Development	16
Evaluation Plan	17
Expert Review and Revision.....	17

Distribution	17
Future Evaluation Plan.....	18
RESULTS: DEPRESSION SCREENING IN ADOLESCENTS – AN ONLINE TRAINING MODULE FOR SCHOOL NURSES	19
DISCUSSION	21
IMPLICATIONS FOR SCHOOL NURSING PRACTICE	24
CONCLUSION	26
REFERENCES	27
APPENDIX A: SCREEN CAPTURES OF THE ONLINE DEPRESSION EDUCATION MODULE	38
APPENDIX B: PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST QUESTIONS.....	45
APPENDIX C: EDUCATION MODULE PRESENTATION SLIDES.....	46
APPENDIX D: SAMPLE PHQ-9 FORM	54
APPENDIX E: DEPRESSION REFERRAL ALGORITHM FOR SCHOOL NURSES	55
APPENDIX F: SAMPLE HEALTH REFERRAL FORM	56
APPENDIX G: EXAMPLE OF A COMPLETED HEALTH REFERRAL FORM...	57
APPENDIX H: MANUSCRIPT FOR NASN SCHOOL NURSE	58
APPENDIX I: PERMISSION TO USE THE PRECEDE-PROCEED FRAMEWORK.....	77
APPENDIX J: PERMISSION TO USE MATERIAL FROM UCLA CENTER FOR MENTAL HEALTH IN SCHOOLS.....	78
APPENDIX K: PERMISSION TO USE VIDEO FROM AMERICAN FOUNDATION OF SUICIDE PREVENTION	79

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. The PRECEDE-PROCEED Model	6
2. Positive influencing factors on depression screening	8

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BACKGROUND

Depression is the leading cause of disability in adolescents worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO], 2014). In the United States, according to the data from the 2013 Youth Risk Behavior Survey (YRBS), 29.9% of high school students reported feeling sad or hopeless almost every day for two or more weeks (Kann et al., 2014). From the same survey, 17% of all high school students had seriously considered attempting suicide. Depression left untreated may lead to suicide, which is the second leading cause of mortality after accidents in the adolescent population (Heron, 2015). Although depression is recognized as being highly prevalent among teenagers, it is underdiagnosed. Early identification of students with depression and proper mental health referral can have a significant impact on reducing the number of cases of suicide in adolescents.

Major depression disorder (MDD), as defined in the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistics Manual of Mental Disorder (DSM-V), presents with five or more of the following symptoms most of the day, almost every day, for at least 2 weeks (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

1. A depressed mood.
2. A loss of interest in all or almost all activities.
3. Significant weight loss or weight gain not due to dieting.
4. Insomnia or oversleeping.
5. Psychomotor agitation or retardation
6. Fatigue or loss of energy.
7. Feelings of worthlessness or guilty.

8. Diminished ability to think or concentrate, or being indecisive.
9. Thoughts of death or suicide, or having a suicide plan.

Young people spend most of their days learning and socializing at school.

Students with depression often exhibit poor academic performance, problems with interpersonal relationships, and difficulties completing assignments and staying on task. They tend to visit the school health office frequently with vague somatic symptoms such as headache, stomach ache, and musculoskeletal pain (Shannon, Bergren, & Matthews, 2010). School nurses, trained in health assessment, health promotion, and disease prevention, are best positioned to identify students with depression.

School nurses are the most highly qualified and educated health care providers in the school setting. Many school nurses are licensed registered nurses (RNs) with bachelor degrees and have completed specialized school health service training, usually at a graduate level credential program, to provide health services in schools. Some also hold advanced graduate degrees in nursing or education. These highly trained health professionals are responsible for many essential health services such as day to day office visits, minor or major emergencies, vision, hearing, dental, and scoliosis screening, acute and chronic disease management, health assessments for children with special needs, and many other health promotion and prevention programs. Because the school nurse is often the first health professional a depressed youth will see, therefore, it is important that they are able to recognize these young persons in distress and refer them timely for care.

Problem Statement

The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) and United States Preventive Service Task Force (USPSTF) both recommend depression screening as part of

adolescent routine well visit in the primary care setting (Geoffrey, 2014; USPSTF, 2016). Despite this recommendation, the screening rates remain very low (Zenlea, Milliren, Mednick, & Rhodes, 2014). The Behavioral Health Barometer: United States, a report published by the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA), showed an alarming increase in the number of adolescents meeting the fourth edition of Diagnostic and Statistics Manual of Mental Disorder (DSM-IV) criteria for having a major depression episode (MDE) from about 8.3% in 2008 to 11.4% in 2014 (SAMHSA, 2013; SAMHSA, 2015). Unfortunately, almost 60% of those with MDE did not received any treatment (SAMHSA, 2015). Green et al. (2013), in their study on adolescent mental health service utilization, found that fewer than half of youths with a DSM-IV diagnosis received mental health services. The gap between adolescents with depression and those who were identified and treated is great.

Although evidence has shown improved detection and outcome when primary care providers (PCPs) screen for depression, adolescents are not routinely screened in the primary care setting. Studies have shown that many of our nation's youth do not receive regular medical care. About one third of adolescents age 12 to 17 have not seen their PCPs for more than six months (Bloom & Freeman, 2015). Even if they present themselves to their PCPs, few are screened (McGoey, Huang, & Palmes, 2013; Zenlea et al., 2014). Reasons for PCPs not screening include lack of time, lack of referral resources, lack of knowledge and training, and limited reimbursement (Diamond et al., 2012; Sanders, 2006). These barriers also exist in the school setting. The lack of time, high workload, lack of knowledge on screening, lack of screening tool, lack of resources to follow up, all contribute to low screening and referral rates (Bohnenkamp, Stephan, &

Bobo, 2015; Pryjmachuk, Graham, Haddad, & Tylee, 2012). An increased awareness of adolescent depression and an evidence-based learning module for screening and referral can help increase school nurses' confidence in depression screening and the rate of screening and referral.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this project is to develop an evidence-based adolescent depression screening education module for school nurses. This education module will include facts on adolescent depression, signs and symptoms, information on the proper use of an evidence based screening tool, and an algorithm for referral and follow up. It is anticipated that by providing training to school nurses, there will be an increased awareness and understanding of adolescent depression, and will lead to greater confidence in assessment, screening, and referral. Thus, more adolescent students with depressive symptoms can be identified early and treated in a timely manner.

Conceptual Framework

Crosby and Noar (2011) describe the importance of having a planning model for any kind of health promotion effort. Identifying a conceptual framework or model to guide the development of the adolescent depression screening learning module is essential. A framework allows the planner to examine the subject matter thoroughly and follow a step-by-step approach to avoid missing important details. The PRECEDE portion of the PRECEDE-PROCEED model was selected as a guiding framework for the development of this learning module.

The PRECEDE-PROCEED Model (PPM), conceptualized by Green in 1974, is a widely used systematic approach to health promotion and public health intervention

program development (Green & Kreuter, 1999). There are many successful applications of the PPM model in the literature in health promotion and education programs (Buta et al., 2011; Kattelman et al., 2014; Manios et al., 2012; Moshki, Dehnoalian, & Alami, 2016; Nadrian, Morowatisharifabad, & Bahmanpour, 2011; Peterson, 2012). The acronym, PRECEDE, stands for predisposing, reinforcing, and enabling constructs in educational/ecological diagnosis and evaluation. PRECEDE includes five phases of assessment which allow health program planners to adequately examine the personal, social, cultural, behavioral, and environmental factors of a targeted population (Green & Kreuter, 1999). By examining the characteristics of the population and their unique barriers to adopting health promoting behavior, a culturally tailored intervention or education program can be created to improve health outcomes and quality of life of the targeted group (Green & Kreuter, 1999). The second part of the model, PROCEED, stands for policy, regulatory, and organizational constructs in educational and environmental development. PROCEED encompasses four additional phases related to implementation and evaluation (See Figure 1). Phases one through five make up PRECEDE while phases six through nine are the PROCEED steps. All nine phases are described below.

Figure 1. The PRECEDE-PROCEED Model. Adapted from “Health Program Planning: An Educational and Ecological Approach,” by L. W. Green and M. W. Kreuter, 3th Edition, 1999, p. 35.

Phase One – Social Assessment

The first step in planning any activity to improve a health outcome in a targeted community or population is to assess the unique characteristics of the population including health values, culture, accessibility and barriers to care, and level of trust with health providers (Crosby & Noar, 2011). For this project, an understanding of how depression manifests in the teenage population is essential to determine the most effective interventions to improve quality of life of these young people.

Phase Two – Epidemiological Assessment

In this phase a review of current data on prevalence of depression in teenagers and the rate of diagnosis and treatment, including screening rates, provides information about

the scope and impact of the health issue (Green & Kreuter, 1999). Better understanding of the prevalence of the problem leads to setting clear goals for the program.

Phase Three – Behavioral and Environmental Assessment

After establishing the goals of the program, the next step is to determine what behavioral or environmental factors can be modified to achieve the goal. In the case of adolescent depression, the low rate of depression screening in both in primary care clinics and in the school setting appear to be a key concern (Bohnenkamp et al., 2015; Prymachuk et al., 2012). Further investigation and identification of health providers' knowledge, attitudes, and barriers to screening will lead to a better understanding of how the education module can focus on significant areas of concern to improve screening rates.

Phase Four – Educational and Ecological Assessment

This phase includes identification of factors that influence behavior. Green and Kreuter (1999) described three types of factors which will impact behavior: predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing. Predisposing factors generally look at knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, values, perceived needs and abilities. Enabling factors consist of availability, accessibility, affordability of the health improving measure. Reinforcing factors include social support, peer influence, positive or negative feedback. Together, these factors can affect a health behavior positively or negatively. The targeted behavior in this project is to increase rates of depression screening. In order to exert a positive influence on school nurses' screening behavior, all relevant predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing factors will be considered when designing the education module (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Positive influencing factors on depression screening.

Phase Five – Administrative and Policy Assessment

During this phase, an assessment of the organizational factors associated with the intervention are investigated. Factors such as time, human resources, and budget must be considered (Green & Kreuter, 1999). Also, at the organization level, it is important to determine whether the program aligns with the organization mission, policies, and regulations to allow for smooth implementation. Because school districts often rely on attendance for revenue, early identification and treatment of depression in students will reduce absenteeism due to the debilitating consequence of depression. It is important for school administrators and policy makers to understand the need to empower school

nurses to be aware of depression and be confident in identifying and taking care of students showing signs and symptoms.

Phase Six – Implementation

During phase six the intervention program is implemented. For this project, rather than wide-ranging implementation, the education module will be reviewed by a small group of experience school nurses and experts in the field for appraisal and feedback.

Phases Seven through Nine – Process, Impact, and Outcome Evaluation

Evaluation is an important step in the process to determine if the intervention program is effective. Process evaluation determines if there are any problems related to administrative issues such as logistics and timing (Green & Kreuter, 1999). Impact evaluation looks at the effect of the program on the targeted health behavior. Finally, outcome evaluation examines whether the program achieved its initial goal of an improved quality of life. An evaluation plan will be developed to determine the effectiveness of the education module in increasing school nurses' confidence and competency in screening symptomatic adolescent for depression in the future.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Method

A thorough search of literature for this project was performed using CINAHL (ESBCO) and PubMed databases. The search was conducted with the following limits: peer-reviewed, English-language, and published between year 2006 to 2016. In order to better understand adolescent depression screening, the search term “depression screening” was placed in the title field with keywords “adolescents,” “adolescence,” “teens,” “teenagers,” “youth,” or “school” in the abstract field.

Because it is important to understand factors affecting depression screening both in primary care and school settings, a search of literature to examine providers’ perception and attitude was also performed. For this search the term “depression screening” was placed in the title field and keywords “attitudes” or “perceptions” or “beliefs” or “views” in the abstract field.

Finally, a valid and reliable screening tool is needed for depression screening in the adolescent population. The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 is widely used in the primary care setting because it is short and can be obtained easily at no cost. A review of literature was performed to determine if this screening tool is validated for use in the adolescent population. The search was done using the keywords “Patient Health Questionnaire,” “PHQ,” “PHQ-9,” “PHQ9,” “PHQ-A,” or “PHQA” in the title field, and “adolescents,” “adolescence,” “teens,” “teenagers,” “youth,” or “school” in the abstract field.

The Importance of Adolescent Depression Screening in Schools

Adolescence is an important developmental stage when immense physical, intellectual, and psychological changes take place. This stage is characterized by a search for identity and a desire for acceptance by peers. Young people who have difficulties accomplishing these developmental tasks are especially vulnerable to developing major depression. There is abundance of literature showing the negative effect of depression on attendance and academic performance, social well-being, and risky behaviors (McCarty et al., 2013; Montag et al., 2015; Riglin, Petrides, Frederickson, & Rice, 2014; Verboom, Sijtsema, Verhulst, Penninx, & Ormel, 2013). At-risk youth are more likely to suffer from MDEs, anxiety disorder, substance abuse, and violence as they grow into adulthood (Bhatia & Bhatia, 2007; Merikangas, He, & Burstein, 2010). Longitudinal data reveals a significant correlation between future criminal behavior and adolescent depression (Anderson, Cesur, & Tekin, 2015). The economic and social burden of depression on society and the detrimental effects on the physical and mental health of the individual are enormous. Therefore, early identification and treatment in adolescents is paramount.

Besides home, adolescents spend most of their time at school. Because school nurses are the health experts in the schools, they are valuable advisers for students to deal with their physical and emotional health needs. The National Association of School Nurses (NASN) emphasizes the unique position of the school nurse as a leader in coordinating school mental health services (NASN, 2013). This affirms the role of the school nurse in assessing, referring, and following-up on students with both physical and mental health problems. One of the major functions of the school nurse is health

screening. School nurses are trained to perform health assessments such as growth and development, vision, hearing, dental, and scoliosis screening. Literature provides evidence that school-based screening programs are feasible and effective in early identification of depression in adolescents (Allison, Nativio, Mitchell, Ren, & Yuhasz, 2014; Carnevale, 2011; Carnevale, 2012).

Both the AAP and USPSTF recommend depression screening for all adolescents. Depression screening in the school setting can be done two ways. It can be done both as a school- or district-wide screening program, or school nurses can do it as the need arises during day-to-day encounters. Universal screening, which is the screening of all adolescent students, is a cost-effective way to identify students with depressive symptoms so that early treatment is possible. However, there has been much controversy about student rights and privacy, anxiety, stigma, and unnecessary medication and treatment due to false positive screening results (Lehrman, 2006). As a result, universal screening has not been widely adopted in public school districts. Need-based screening, on the other hand, focuses on students who present themselves to the health office or are referred by the teachers. By improving understanding and awareness of adolescent depression and learning how to use a validated depression screening tool, school nurses will be better equipped to identify and refer students in need.

Providers' Attitudes, Perceptions, and Beliefs in Adolescent Depression Screening

While many health care providers believe that it is prudent to screen for depression during routine office visits, the actual rate of screening is very low (Cronholm et al., 2010; Sanders, 2006; Zenlea et al., 2014; Zuckerbrot et al., 2007). The data obtained from the National Ambulatory Medical Care Survey and the National Hospital

Ambulatory Care Survey showed only 0.2% of documented depression screening during the 46,347 ambulatory care visits surveyed (Zenlea et al., 2014). A number of studies were conducted to identify the barriers preventing providers from screening. These barriers include limited time and resources, lack of training, culture and language competency, and the long wait for mental health referral (Cronholm et al., 2010; Kim et al., 2009; Rhondali et al., 2012, Segre, Pollack, Brock, Andrew, & O'Hara, 2014; Tabb et al., 2015; Taliaferro et al, 2013). Providers, in general, favor the use of a depression screening tool and screening rates improve after the implementation of a standardized screening tool (Lewandows et al., 2016; Sanders et al, 2016; Segre et al, 2014; Ski, Munian, Rolley, & Thompson, 2015; Taliaferro et al., 2013).

Limited studies on depression screening have been conducted in the school setting. A poll conducted by NASN reflected findings similar to those in the primary care setting (Carnevale, 2012). In response to the poll, most school nurses reported that they are not currently screening for mental health problems citing the lack of training, the lack of screening tool, and the lack of referral sources as the top reasons (Bohnenkamp et al., 2015). An education module on depression screening, and providing instruction on the use of a standardized tool will likely increase depression screening among school nurses.

Depression Screening Tool for Adolescent in the School Setting

There are a number of well validated and reliable depression screening tools available for screening adolescents. To facilitate the screening process, the ideal tool needs to be easy to use, free or low cost, and require short administration and scoring time. The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) is a nine-item self-reported survey used to identify depressive symptoms and suicidal risk. It is available free of charge in

the public domain and is easy to administer, taking about a minute to complete. The PHQ-9 has been validated in primary care settings for adolescents to detect clinical depression with a good sensitivity of 89.5% and specificity of 77.5% at a cutoff score of 11 (Richardson et al., 2010). Although, psychometrics at various cutoff score yield different sensitivity and specificity, it is agreed by most researchers that the PHQ-9 is a valid and reliable tool for adolescent screening (Allgaier, Pietsch, Fruhe, Sigl-Glockner, & Schulte-Korne, 2012; Ganguly et al., 2013; Richardson et al., 2010; Tsai et al., 2014). Although the USPSTF has recommended PHQ-A as a screening tool for adolescents, it has not been widely adopted in the primary care or the school setting. The PHQ-A is a self-reported 67-item survey needing longer time to administer and score and it requires publisher permission before use. Taking all the above factors into consideration, the PHQ-9 is a preferred screening tool for school nurses to use.

The review of literature revealed limited data available in the area of depression screening by school nurses in the school setting. In order to increase school nurses' knowledge and awareness on adolescent depression, and increase confidence in screening, additional training is necessary. An online education module focused on the subject matter and how to use the PHQ-9 as a screening tool is a cost-effective way to provide training to school nurses.

PROJECT GOALS & OBJECTIVES

The goal of this project is to develop an education module on depression screening for school nurses. The objectives are as follows:

1. Describe the current status of adolescent depression and screening practices in the school setting in the United States.
2. Review clinical guidelines and expert recommendations for depression screening in adolescents.
3. Assess the use of the Pediatric Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) for depression screening in the adolescent population in schools.
4. Develop an education module on adolescent depression screening for school nurses including a fact/information sheet, valid PHQ-9 screening tool, scoring guide, algorithm for referral and follow up.
5. Develop an evaluation plan to determine the effectiveness of the learning module in increasing the confidence of school nurses in screening and referral of students with depression symptoms in the future.

METHOD

The purpose of this project is to develop an education module on adolescent depression screening using the PHQ-9 for school nurses.

Target Population and Setting

The intended education module is being developed for school nurses who work with middle and high school students anywhere in the United States.

Ethical Consideration

The development of this education module will not involve human subject testing. Therefore, this project does not require the review and approval of the institutional review board.

Content Research

In order to ensure a solid understanding of depression in adolescents, a literature review will be conducted using the academic databases CINAHL, PubMed, and EBSCO, and internet web sites of associated professional organizations to obtain current information on epidemiology of adolescent depression, diagnosis and treatment, clinical recommendations, and guidelines. Additional information and expert opinions on adult learning theories and principles of online education module development was sought throughout the development of this education module.

Education Module Development

Because the internet allows for the convenient and flexible delivery of content to a large audience, the presentation was expected to be available online for school nurses to access at their convenience. The presentation was developed using Adobe PowerPoint

with professional voice over narration. The following sections were included in the education module:

1. Training Module
 - a. Pre-test
 - b. Main Presentation
 - c. Post-test
2. PHQ-9 (Screening Tool Links)
3. Referral Algorithm & Form
4. Resources
5. Recommended Video (*More Than Sad* by American Foundation for Suicide Prevention)

Evaluation Plan

Expert Review and Revision

A small group of experienced school nurses, school health managers, and nursing faculty was invited to review the education module for feedbacks on content, user friendliness, and adult learning. The module was revised after feedback was collected.

Distribution

The finished product was made available online and will be distributed to school nurses via email invitation through contact persons at local or state professional school nurse organizations and school districts. A manuscript will be submitted to the NASN School Nurse to raise awareness of depression screening in adolescents and to provide information for school nurses to access the education module.

Future Evaluation Plan

After the completion of the development of this education module, further investigation can be done to evaluate the effectiveness of this training on school nurses' knowledge and attitudes about depression and rates of screening. Data will be collected in the form of a survey before participation in the depression screening training and six months after the training, to determine if the education module results in any change in practice.

RESULTS: DEPRESSION SCREENING IN ADOLESCENTS – AN ONLINE TRAINING MODULE FOR SCHOOL NURSES

After comparing various delivery model and platform, the depression screening education module was developed using Google Sites for content delivery and Google Forms for future data collection. The main training PowerPoint presentation was exported as a video and embedded in the education module for viewing on a computer or a mobile device. The education module is accessible online at <https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscreeningtraining>. The module home menu will allow school nurses access to training materials, the PHQ9 screener, sample referral form and resources (Appendix A). The following is a detailed list of all the sections included:

1. Training Module
 - a. Pre-test (Appendix B)
 - b. Main Presentation (Appendix C)
 - i. Introduction to Adolescent Depression: Background, Epidemiology, Diagnostic Criteria using DSM-V
 - ii. Signs and Symptoms of Depression, Factors associated with Depression
 - iii. The Role of School Nurses
 - iv. Using PHQ-9 as a screening tool, Validity and Reliability, Scoring and Interpretation
 - v. Referral Algorithm and Follow Up
 - vi. A Summary Case Study
 - c. Post-test (Appendix B)

2. PHQ-9 (Link to a sample PHQ-9 Form and to PHQ-9 screeners in other languages) (Appendix D)
3. Referral Algorithm (Appendix E), Referral Form (Appendix F), and Sample referral form (Appendix G)
4. Resources
5. Recommended Video (More Than Sad by American Foundation for Suicide Prevention)

Also, in addition to the education module, a manuscript will be submitted to NASN School Nurse to further increase awareness of the importance of depression screening in adolescents and promote access to the online training education module (Appendix H).

DISCUSSION

Using the PRECEDE-PROCEED framework, a comprehensive examination of the issue of teenage depression reveals the importance of screening by school nurses who are at the forefront of combating this problem. In order to improve identification and referral of depressed teenagers, the literature review demonstrated the need to increase school nurses' knowledge on adolescent depression and provide them with an evidence-based, low cost, and easy to use screening tool. As a result, an online education module was developed to address these needs.

Prior to the development of this education module, characteristics and learning preferences of school nurses was taken into consideration. The 2015 NASN School Nurse Survey polled 8,006 respondents in 50 states and revealed that 67.2% were between 41 to 60 years old (Maughan & Mangena, 2015). Many school nurses felt that self-paced web-based educational program best fit their schedule (Maughan & Mangena, 2014). The depression education module is therefore developed as a self-paced web-based program accessible to school nurses anytime, anywhere. In addition, the majority of the school nurses today encompasses the late baby boomers and Generation X nurses who are the among first to adopt computer and internet technology (Pesta, 2014). It is important to recognize the different comfort level with technology while designing the module. The training module should be simple, user friendly, and readily accessible to encourage participation in the training.

Besides learner characteristics, it is important to take into consideration individual learning style. The education module incorporates many of the teaching strategies that will engage nurses with different learning styles. According to the Visual, Aural,

Read/Write, Kinesthetic sensory (VARK) modalities, the four major learning modalities as depicted in the acronym are used to guide the design and development of the training module (Fleming & Mills, 1992; VARK Learn Limited, 2017). The depression education module utilizes a video presentation with colorful graphics and charts, which is preferred by the visual learners. A professional voice over alongside the video presentation helps engage the aural learners. The handouts, bulleted slides, and the resource list provide the information and inputs reading/writing learner needs. Lastly, for the kinesthetic learners, the incorporation of a case study at the end of the presentation sums up the important takeaways from the training from a real-life perspective.

Moreover, there were a number of other things taken into consideration during the development of the training module including type of presentation software, hosting, cost, accessibility, and the possibility of data collection in the future. It was determined that an online website developed using Google Sites was sufficient for the purpose of this module. The presentation content can be viewed on desktop computers or mobile devices such as laptops, tablets, or smart phones and is easily accessible to accommodate the busy schedule of the school nurses. The Pre-test and Post-test were developed using Google Forms and integrated with the module seamlessly to allow for future data collection and analysis. The module site provides the PHQ-9 survey in English and in other languages, printable referral form, referral algorithm, and resource links, which makes it convenient for the school nurse to obtain information on adolescent depression screening whenever needed.

After the completion of the education module, a small group of experience school nurses and nurse educators were asked to review the module and provide feedback for

improvement. The feedback was overwhelmingly positive and encouraging. Most reviewers felt that the content of the training was important to school nurses, which aligns with the 2015 NASN School Nurse Survey findings where one third of the respondents identified depression as a topic of education need (Maughan & Mangena, 2015). After viewing the presentation all reviewers expressed increased confidence in their ability to administer and interpret the PHQ-9 test and recommend this depression education module as a training tool to increase the knowledge and competence of adolescent depression screening in school nurses. Some pre-test and post-test questions were modified according to the expert nurse educator's recommendations to improve the clarity and readability of the questions.

In order to increase school nurses' knowledge and competency in adolescent depression screening, it is recommended that the online adolescent depression screening education module be promoted and disseminated via various channels to reach a broader school nurse audience. School Nurses will be able to learn more about the education module via poster presentation at the NASN school nurse conference in San Diego in June and a manuscript to NASN School Nurse Journal. Both the poster presentation and manuscript are pending acceptance. Future dissemination activities aimed at sharing the education module for professional development include presentation of the education module at professional conferences organized by NASN, California School Nurse Organization, local School Health Program Manager Meetings, and via professional networking with school nurse colleagues. School nurses are encouraged to share this online adolescent depression education module with their peers and colleagues.

IMPLICATIONS FOR SCHOOL NURSING PRACTICE

The National Association of School Nurses (2013), in its position statement on mental health in students, emphasized the vital role of school nurses in “identifying students struggling with mental, psychosocial or emotional issues, which, when not recognized, may affect educational achievement and development of full academic potential.” Indeed, the ultimate goal of school nursing practice is to help students reach their full academic potential through an array of activities of health promotion and disease prevention. It is imperative that school nurses understand the detrimental effects of depression on the physical, emotional, and social well-being, and academic performance of students. Providing additional training to school nurses via an online education module is cost effective way to increase the ability of school nurses to care for students with mental health problems.

With the introduction of Affordable Care Act and the expansion of the Medicaid program across the nation, the increased demand on health care services, especially mental health services, has placed a tremendous burden on the already overload healthcare system. With a serious shortage in mental health providers and low reimbursement rate, there has been a trend to shift mental health services into the primary care and school setting. The Mental Health in Schools Act [H.R. 1211] (2015) was introduced to provide federal funding for comprehensive school based mental health programs and improve the link between the schools and community mental health agencies. The role of school nurse in school mental health service is becoming more imperative. In addition to being expert in assessment and referral, the school nurse plays an important role in care coordination to facilitate communication and collaboration

between student and family, school teachers and counselors, health care providers, third party payors, and community agencies so that the comprehensive health needs of the student can be met (McClanahan & Weismuller, 2014). It is best practice for school nurses to keep a current and periodically updated list of local mental health providers and agencies for referral to ensure students are able to obtain the care they need. A student with severe depression and significant academic difficulty may be eligible for educational services and school counseling services under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) or Section 504. In such a case, the school nurse will work with the student, the family, and the school personnel to develop an individualized education program with specialized instruction or counseling services so that the student can reach his or her academic goals.

Every school district should establish clear policy and procedures regarding mental health screening based on the needs of its student population, availability of resources, and the recommendation of the school mental health professionals. The school nurse should be actively involved in district wellness and mental health policymaking. As the health expert in the education setting, the school nurse can provide valuable input and recommendations surrounding how to best serve and advocate for adolescent students with depression and their families. It is important that the school nurse reviews, updates, and revises health policies periodically so that these policies reflect current evidence-based practice guidelines, and ensures confidentiality and compliance while caring for depressed students.

CONCLUSION

Adolescent depression is a silent epidemic in society and the consequences of untreated depression can be devastating. School nurses, being the most accessible health care provider in the school setting, are best positioned to help bridge the mental health service gap for the students. It is important that school nurses are trained to recognize and screen for adolescent depression. An online education module on adolescent depression screening developed for school nurses is a cost-effective way for nurses to access training easily and ab lib. By increasing awareness and knowledge of adolescent depression and promoting the use of PHQ-9, an evidence based screening tool, school nurses will be able to help depressed students and their families access mental health services to obtain the treatments and therapies they desperately need so that they can function optimally at home and at school.

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APPENDIX A

SCREEN CAPTURES OF THE ONLINE DEPRESSION SCREENING EDUCATION MODULE

Depression Screening - T x

Secure | <https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscre>

Depression Screening Home **Training Module** PHQ-9 Referral Algorithm & Form More

TRAINING MODULE

[PRE-TEST](#)

Depression Screening Training

Depression in Adolescents: Early Identification and Screening

An Education Module for School Nurses

[POST-TEST](#)

[Return to Home](#)

Pre-Test

Depression in Adolescents: Early Identification and Screening - An Education Module for School Nurses

* Required

1. What percentage of the adolescent population meets the DSM-V diagnostic criteria of having depression? *

- 1%
- 5%
- 11%
- 20%

2. Why is it important for the school nurse to screen for depression in adolescents? *

Post-Test

Depression in Adolescents: Early Identification and Screening - An Education Module for School Nurses

* Required

Email address *

Your email

1. What percentage of the adolescent population meets the DSM-V diagnostic criteria of having depression? * 1 point

- 1%
- 5%
- 11%
- 20%

Severity Measure for Depression—Child Age 11–17*
*PHQ-9 modified for Adolescents (PHQ-A)—Adapted

Name: _____ Age: _____ Sex: Male Female Date: _____

Instructions: How often have you been bothered by each of the following symptoms during the past 2 weeks? For each symptom put an "X" in the box beneath the answer that best describes how you have been feeling.

	00 Not at all	01 Several days	02 More than half the days	03 Nearly every day	04 Every day
1. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless?					
2. Little interest or pleasure in doing things?					
3. Trouble falling asleep, staying asleep, or sleeping too much?					
4. Poor appetite, weight loss, or gaining weight?					
5. Feeling tired or having little energy?					
6. Feeling bad about yourself—or feeling that you are a failure, or that you have let yourself or your family down?					
7. Trouble concentrating on things like school work, reading, or watching TV?					
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed?					
9. Or the opposite—being so fidgety or restless that you were moving around a lot more than usual?					
10. Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or all hurting yourself in some way?					
Total/Partial Raw Score:					
Presented Total Raw Score (of 27 items left unanswered):					

*Reprinted from the PHQ-9 (© 2002) for research and evaluation purposes.

Page 1 / 2

PHQ-9 (OTHER LANGUAGES)

[Return to Home](#)

Depression Screening - P X

Secure | <https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscreeningtraining/referral-algorithm-form>

Depression Screening Home Training Module PHQ-9 **Referral Algorithm & Form** Resources Recommended Video

REFERRAL ALGORITHM & FORM

REFERRAL ALGORITHM

Referral

```

graph TD
    A[Symptomatic Adolescent] --> B[PHQ-9 < 10  
None - Mild]
    A --> C[PHQ-9 ≥ 10  
Moderate - Severe]
    A --> D[Suicide Ideation]
    B --> E[Check-in  
As needed]
    C --> F[Initiate Parent  
Conference]
    F --> G[Obtain Release of Medical  
Information]
    G --> H[Refer to  
Primary Care/  
Mental Health]
    G --> I[Refer to School  
Mental Health  
Professionals]
    H --> J[Follow Up in  
Short Interval]
    I --> J
    D --> K[School Suicide  
Prevention/  
Crisis Protocol]
  
```

REFERRAL FORM

[Health Referral Form](#)

[Health Referral Form \(Example\)](#)

Depression Screening - F X

Secure | <https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscreeningtraining/resources>

Depression Screening Home Training Module PHQ-9 Referral Algorithm & Form **Resources** Recommended Video

RESOURCES

[American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry - Facts for Families - The Depressed Child](#)

[Center for Epidemiological Studies – Depression Scale for Children](#)

[Child Mind Institute](#)

[Kids Health - Depression](#)

[National Alliance on Mental Illness - Depression](#)

[National Association Of School Nurses – Mental Health](#)

[National Institute of Mental Health - Depression](#)

[National Mental Health Association - Depression in Teens](#)

[University of Maryland - School Mental Health](#)

[UCLA Center for Mental Health in Schools](#)

[Return to Home](#)

Depression Screening - f X

Secure | https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscreeningtraining/recommended-video

Depression Screening Home Training Module PHQ-9 Referral Algorithm & Form Resources Recommended Video

RECOMMENDED VIDEO

More Than Sad - Teen Depression
from WSTX Television

25:29 HD :: vimeo

**THIS VIDEO IS AVAILABLE FOR PURCHASE ONLINE AT
AMERICAN FOUNDATION FOR SUICIDE PREVENTION**

[Return to Home](#)

APPENDIX B

PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST QUESTIONS

1. What percentage of the adolescent population meets the DSM-V diagnostic criteria of having depression?
 - a. 1%
 - b. 5%
 - c. 11%
 - d. 20%
2. Why is it important to screen for depression in adolescents?
 - a. Early identification and referral saves lives
 - b. Effective depression treatment for adolescents are available.
 - c. Treating depression improves psychosocial well-being and academic performance
 - d. All of the above
3. Which ONE of the following physical sign or symptom is NOT commonly seen in a depressed adolescent?
 - a. Poor appetite
 - b. Hyperactivity
 - c. Stomach ache
 - d. Headache
 - e. Neglected appearance
4. Which ONE of the following behavioral problems is NOT commonly seen in a depressed adolescent?
 - a. Problems with family and peer relationships
 - b. Difficulties completing and staying on tasks
 - c. Poor academic performance
 - d. Substance use
 - e. Spending too much time with friends
5. The PHQ-9 cut-off score that warrants further medical evaluation for major depression is:
 - a. 5
 - b. 11
 - c. 15
 - d. 21
6. A 15-year-old male student complains of tiredness and stomach ache for the third time this week. He denies fever, chills, body aches, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, cough, runny nose, or sore throat. Student attendance record shows 6 absences in the past 3 months. His PHQ-9 score is 16. How should the school nurse interpret the score?
 - a. Student is at low risk of having depression.
 - b. Student may have moderate depression for which he should be referred for further evaluation by his doctor.
 - c. Student may need counseling therapy with or without medication
 - d. B & C
7. When contacting the parent of a depressed student regarding referral to a health provider, which of the factors should the school nurse take into consideration?
 - a. Cultural perspective of depression
 - b. Language proficiency
 - c. Health care coverage and access
 - d. All of the above

APPENDIX C

EDUCATION MODULE TRAINING SLIDES

Learning Objectives

By the end of this education module, the school nurse will be able to:

1. Identify signs and symptoms of depression in adolescents.
2. Describe the role of the school nurse in depression screening.
3. Demonstrate how to score, and interpret the PHQ-9 screening test.
4. Communicate findings and provide appropriate referrals.

Why do we need to screen for depression

- Early identification and referral saves lives
- Effective depression treatments are available - Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and/or antidepressants (SSRIs)
- Treating depression improves psychosocial well being and academic performance
- Improves attendance = increase school revenue

High School Youth Risk Behavior Survey, 2013

	Total (% , C.I.)	Female	Male
Felt Sad Or Hopeless ¹	29.9 (28.3–31.6)	39.1 (36.8–41.4)	20.8 (19.4–22.3)
Seriously Considered Attempting Suicide ²	17.0 (15.8–18.2)	22.4 (20.8–24.0)	11.6 (10.3–12.9)
Attempted Suicide ³	8.0 (7.2–8.9)	10.6 (9.4–11.9)	5.4 (4.5–6.3)

¹ Almost every day for 2 or more weeks in a row some time in the 12 months preceding the survey.
² During the 12 months before the survey.
³ One or more times during the 12 months before the survey.

Source: http://www.cdc.gov/behavioralriskfactorssurvey/data/docs/yrbhs_2013_national_data_report.pdf

Depression vs. Bad Mood

- Severity
- Duration
- Domain

Source: <http://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/stop-guessing-depression-from-normal-adolescent-mood-swings-2010-03-11-119>

Depression vs. Bad Mood

Severity

Severity of Symptoms:

- Changes in mood - anger, sadness, irritability
- Behaviors - sleeping or eating more or less than usual, taking drugs or alcohol, acting out; withdrawing from friends and family
- Feelings - loneliness, insecurity, apathy
- Thoughts - hopelessness, worthlessness, suicidal thoughts
- Perceptual disturbances - pain, hallucinations

Source:
<http://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/distinguishing-depression-from-normal-adolescent-mood-swings-2010/04/15/337>

Depression in Adolescence

Physical Manifestations:

- Tiredness
- Change in Appetite
- Insomnia/hypersomnia
- Irritability
- Headache
- Stomach ache
- Musculoskeletal pain
- Slow thinking / speaking / body movement
- Neglected appearance

(Shannon, Bergson, & Matthews, 2010)

Depression vs. Bad Mood

Duration

- Notable deterioration in behavior or mood that lasts two weeks or longer, without a break
- Dysthymic Disorder, or minor depression - symptoms can persist for even more than a year

Source:
<http://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/distinguishing-depression-from-normal-adolescent-mood-swings-2010/04/15/337>

Depression in Adolescence

Social & Behavioral Manifestations:

- Problems with family and peer relationships
- Difficulties completing and staying on tasks
- Poor academic performance
- Poor Attendance
- Social isolation
- Substance use
- Other Risky Behaviors

Source: Humerick, J., Kuehars, S. A., Page, J., Wells, C., Goodwin, B., & Van Voorhees, B. W. (2010). Adolescents with depressive symptoms and their challenges with learning in school. *The Journal of School Nursing, 25*(5), 377-383.

Depression vs. Bad Mood

Domain

- Problems in different areas functioning — at home, in school, and in interactions with friends
- Difficulties are often not a result of an identifiable event.

Source:
<http://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/distinguishing-depression-from-normal-adolescent-mood-swings-2010/04/15/337>

Risk Factors

Biomedical and Genetic Factors

- Chronic illness (eg. Asthma, Type 1 Diabetes, Seizure Disorder)
- Female sex
- Obesity
- Hormonal changes during puberty
- Parental or family history of depression
- Use of certain medications (eg. Isotretinoin)

Source: Boutelle, K. N., Harran, P., Fulkerson, J. A., Crow, S. J., & Sicks, E. (2010). Obesity as a prospective predictor of depression in adolescent females. *Health Psychology, 29*(3), 293-298. doi:10.1037/a0018945

Risk Factors

Psychosocial factors

- Childhood neglect or abuse (physical, emotional, or sexual)
- History of being bullied
- General stressors - socioeconomic deprivations
- Loss of a loved one, parent, or romantic relationship

Other factors

- Anxiety disorder, ADHD, conduct, or learning disorders
- Cigarette smoking
- History of depression

Source: Boulesteix, K. N., Hamami, F., Fulkerson, J. A., Crow, S. J., & Stice, E. (2010). Obesity as a prospective predictor of depression in adolescent females. *Health Psychology, 29*(3), 293-299. doi:10.1037/a0018645

PHQ-9 – an evidence based tool

- Well studied and validated
 - Score - 11 or higher
 - sensitivity (true positive) - 89.5%
 - specificity (true negative) - 77.5%
 - for identifying youth with major depressive disorder. (Kroenke et al., 2010; Richardson et al., 2010)
- Various cultures and languages (Adwiyas, Ota, & Afolabi, 2006; Cheng, et al., 2012; Gelaye et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2011; Karekla et al., 2012; Ganguly et al., 2012; Wong et al., 2012)

Protective Factors

- Quality relationships in family and school
- No current stressors or losses
- No current alcohol or substance abuse
- No history of physical or sexual abuse
- Good grades
- Involvement with extracurricular activities
- Strong religious belief or faith
- Good problem-solving and coping skills
- Positive and concrete future plans and goals

PHQ-9 – an evidence based tool

- Takes a minute to complete
- Easy to administer, score, and interpret
- Free in the Public Domain
- Widely used in Primary Care Setting
- Available in many languages

Depression Screening Tool

- Validity and Reliability
- Ease of Administration
- Cost
- Access
- Practitioner Competence
- Culture & Linguistic Competence

PHQ-9 modified for Adolescents (PHQ-9A)—Adapted

Name: _____ Age: _____ Sex: Male Female Date: _____

Instructions: How often have you been bothered by each of the following symptoms during the past 2 weeks? For each symptom put an "X" in the box beneath the answer that best describes how you have been feeling.

	(0) Not at all	(1) Several days	(2) More than half the days	(3) Nearly every day	Choose the item score
1. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless?					
2. Little interest or pleasure in doing things?					
3. Trouble falling asleep, staying asleep, or sleeping too much?					
4. Poor appetite, weight loss, or overeating?					
5. Feeling tired or having little energy?					
6. Feeling bad about yourself—or feeling that you are a failure, or that you have let yourself or your family down?					
7. Trouble concentrating on things like school work, reading, or watching TV?					
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed?					
9. Or the opposite—being so fidgety or restless that you were moving around a lot more than usual?					
10. Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself in some way?					
Total/Partial Raw Score:					
Reported Total Raw Score: (if 1, 2 items left unanswered)					

Modified from the PHQ-9 by Johnson, 2002 for research and evaluation purposes.

PHQ-9 Score Interpretation

Total Score	Severity of Depressive Episode	Action
0-4	None - minimal	None
5-9	Mild	Support
10-14	Moderate	Refer & Follow up
15-19	Moderately Severe	Refer & Follow up
20-27	Severe	Refer & Follow up

The Role of School Nurses

- Champion for District Policy on Depression Screening
- Keen observer of students' signs & symptoms
- Care coordinator/ Case Manager
- Advocate for Student and family

Referral

Special Considerations

1. Individual District Policy
2. Referral and Follow Up system
3. Cultural Sensitivity – taboos
4. Co-morbidities e.g. Anxiety disorder, ADHD, eating disorder
5. Suicidal Ideation

NASN Position Statement on Mental Health of Students

“Early identification and treatment of problems place school nurses on the forefront of identifying students struggling with mental, psychosocial or emotional issues, which, when not recognized, may affect educational achievement and development of full academic potential” (Stevenson, 2010)

Case Study

Case Study: Steve

Steve is a 15 year old 9th grader who comes to you for a stomach ache. He has been coming to the health office 3 times for the past month. Upon interviewing him, you find that he hasn't eaten breakfast and he doesn't feel like eating.

Case Study: Steve

You realize that Steve may be depressed. You give him the PHQ-9 screener and asked him to complete it. Steve's PHQ-9 score is 15.

Q: What does this score mean?

A. No Depression

B. Mild

C. Moderate

D. Severe

Case Study: Steve

Checking on the student health record, you notice that he has missed 6 days of school since school has started. You call the teacher for her observation. She reports that he appears uninterested in class, has missing assignments, and is socially withdrawing from peers.

Communicating PHQ-9 Result to Student

School Nurse: *Your score indicated the possibility of you being depressed. For example, you indicated that you have little interest doing things "more than half the days". Can you tell me more about it? (Nurse can go through the survey and talk about the responses.)*

Student: ...

School Nurse: *It must be difficult for you ... (Paraphrase some of the comments the student made.)*

Communicating with a Depressed Student

- Maintain Confidentiality and Privacy
- Ask Open-ended Questions
- Active / Reflective Listening
- Allow Time for Response
- Be Non-judgmental
- Show Empathy
- Be Culturally Appropriate

Communicating with Student

School Nurse: *It is not uncommon for young people to be depressed. Depression, like asthma, or diabetes, is a health condition that requires medical attention ... (Discuss some symptoms and facts about depression in teenagers).*

It is very important that you get an appointment with your doctor to determine what's the cause of your ... (student's symptoms) I will contact your parents and let them know about your symptoms and ask them to take you to the doctor.

Case Study: Steve

You explain to Steve the meaning of the result and call the parents. You urge the parents to take Steve in for a comprehensive physical exam to rule out any physical ailments and to determine the need for counseling and mental health referral.

37

Collaborating with the Providers

- Referral Letter with a copy of student's PHQ-9
- Release of Medical Information

40

Communicating with Parents

School Nurse: (After explaining the background information of Steve's physical complaints, you may say..) *Steve completed a depression screening survey for me which indicated that he may be depressed. It is very important that you take your son to his doctor to find out what's the cause of his symptoms... (student's symptoms) and whether or not he has depression. Would you be able to take him for a checkup? (Explore potential barriers and facilitate access to care.)*

38

Case Study: Steve

At the school site, you call Mrs. Burton, the counselor, regarding your concerns. You ask her to follow up on Steve and initiate interventions to help Steve engage in positive peer relations and meaningful activities at school.

41

Case Study: Steve

You ask the parent to take a copy of the PHQ-9 to the medical provider and obtain a signed **Release of Medical Information** from the parent for future communication with the provider. They agree to follow through with the referral.

39

Collaborating with Teachers, School Mental Health Professionals, and Administrators

- Student Support/Success Team
- 504
- IEP

42

Referral

- Know your local resources
eg. Mental Health Providers / Non Profit Organizations and Agencies

**Thank You
for Your Participation**

Follow up

- Short intervals – once a week for the first 2-4 weeks
- Then transition to every other week to once a month based on individual need of the student
- Also needed to check on student's progress with treatment periodically

In Summary

1. Depression is highly prevalent among adolescents.
2. Depression is often underdiagnosed and treated.
3. School nurses, as the health expert in the school setting, has an important role in identifying and referring students with depression.
4. The PHQ-9 depression screening tool can be easily administered and used in the school setting.
5. With proper referral and treatment, adolescents with depressive disorders will be able to attain their full academic potential and be productive in their lives.

APPENDIX D

SAMPLE PHQ-9 FORM

Instructions: How often have you been bothered by each of the following symptoms during the past 7 days? For each symptom put an “X” in the box beneath the answer that best describes how you have been feeling.					Clinician Use
	(0) Not at all	(1) Several days (1-3 days)	(2) More than half the days (4-5 days)	(3) Nearly every day	Item Score
1. Feeling down, depressed, irritable, or hopeless?					
2. Little interest or pleasure in doing things?					
3. Trouble falling asleep, staying asleep, or sleeping too much?					
4. Poor appetite, weight loss or overeating?					
5. Feeling tired, or having little energy?					
6. Feeling bad about yourself – or feeling that you are a failure, or that you have let yourself or your family down?					
7. Trouble concentrating on things like school work, reading, or watching TV?					
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite – being so fidgety or restless that you were moving around a lot more than usual?					
9. Thoughts that you would better off dead, or of hurting yourself in some way?					
Total/Partial Raw Score:					
Prorated Total Raw Score: (if 1 or 2 items left unanswered)					

APPENDIX E

DEPRESSION REFERRAL ALGORITHM FOR SCHOOL NURSES

Referral

APPENDIX F

SAMPLE HEALTH REFERRAL FORM

School: _____ Date: _____

A. Dear Parent/Guardian:

_____ has been seen at school today and the following conditions were noted:
(Student Name)

Further evaluation is recommended at this time. Please take your child and this form to your own doctor as soon as possible. If you need further information or assistance, please contact:

(Name) (Title) (Phone #)

Thank you for your cooperation.

B. Dear Doctor:

Please complete this report and have student return it to the school health office. Thank you.

_____ was seen on _____
(Student Name) (Date)

and was found to have the following:

Treatment/Referral/Recommendations for school:

Provider Name/Title Signature Phone Number

APPENDIX G

EXAMPLE OF A COMPLETED HEALTH REFERRAL FORM

School: ABC High School Date: 1/5/2017

A. Dear Parent/Guardian:

Steven Smith has been seen at school today and the following conditions were noted:
(Student Name)

frequent complaint of headache, lack of appetite, loss of interest in school work, and
a PHQ-9 depression screening score of 16 (may attach a copy of the screening form)

Further evaluation is recommended at this time. Please take your child and this form to your own doctor as soon as possible. If you need further information or assistance, please contact:

Jane Doe, RN School Nurse 800-123-4567
(Name) (Title) (Phone #)

Thank you for your cooperation.

B. Dear Doctor:

Please complete this report and have student return it to the school health office. Thank you.

_____ was seen on _____
(Student Name) (Date)

and was found to have the following:

Treatment/Referral/Recommendations for school:

Provider Name/Title Signature Phone Number

APPENDIX H
MANUSCRIPT FOR NASN SCHOOL NURSE

Abstract

Adolescent depression is a silent epidemic in this country. Untreated depression has detrimental effects on physical health, psychosocial well-being, and academic productivity. It is important for school nurses to be able to recognize depression and refer students promptly for treatment. This article and its associated learning module will provide school nurses with updated information on adolescent depression, discuss barriers in depression screening, utilize the PHQ-9 questionnaire as an evidence based depression screening tool in the educational setting, and the important role of school nurses in depression screening. It is anticipated that by increasing awareness and knowledge about adolescent depression and providing training in the use of an evidence based screening tool, school nurses will have greater confidence in identifying and referring students in need. (Free Online Depression Screening Education Module available at: <https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscreeningtraining>)

Keywords:

1. Adolescent depression
2. Mental health
3. Depression screening
4. School nurse
5. PHQ-9
6. Education module
7. Training

Background

Depression is the leading cause of disability in adolescents worldwide (World Health Organization, 2014). In the United States, according to the data from the 2013 Youth Risk Behavior Survey, 29.9% of high school students reported feeling sad or hopeless almost every day for two or more weeks (Kann et al., 2014). From the same survey, 17% of high school students had seriously considered attempting suicide (Kann et al., 2014). Depression left untreated may lead to suicide, the second leading cause of mortality after accidents in the adolescent population (Heron, 2015). Although depression is recognized as being highly prevalent among teenagers, it is underdiagnosed. Early identification of students with depression, and proper mental health referral, can have a significant impact on reducing the number of cases of suicide in adolescent youths.

Major depression disorder, as defined in the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistics Manual of Mental Disorder (DSM-V), is characterized by the presence of five or more of these symptoms: depressed mood, decreased interest in activities, significant weight loss or weight gain, sleep disturbance, psychomotor agitation or retardation, loss of energy, and self-worth doubts, difficulties with concentration, and suicidal thoughts, most of the day or almost every day for at least two weeks (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. DSM-V diagnostic elements for depression.

Young people spend most of their days learning and socializing at school. Students with depression often exhibit poor academic performance, problems with interpersonal relationships, and difficulties completing assignments and staying on task. Depressed students tend to visit the school health office frequently with vague somatic symptoms such as headache, stomachache, and musculoskeletal pain (Shannon, Bergren, & Matthews, 2010). Untreated depression often leads to violence towards self and others, substance abuse, and other risky behaviors (Humensky et al., 2010). School nurses must be able to recognize these young people in distress and refer them for care.

Current Problem

The American Academy of Pediatrics and United States Preventive Service Task Force (USPSTF) recommend depression screening as part of adolescent routine well-care visit in the primary care setting (Geoffrey, 2014; USPSTF, 2016). Despite this the screening rates remain very low (Zenlea, Milliren, Mednick, & Rhodes, 2014). *The Behavioral Health Barometer: United States*, published by the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA), showed an alarming increase in the number of adolescents meeting the diagnostic criteria of having a major depression episode (MDE) from about 8.3% in 2008 to 11.4% in 2014 (SAMHSA, 2013; SAMHSA, 2015). However, of those who had a MDE, 58.8% did not receive any treatment (SAMHSA, 2015). Green et al. (2013), in their study on adolescent mental health service utilization, found that fewer than half of the youths with a psychiatric diagnosis received mental health services. The gap between adolescents with depression and those who were identified and treated is great.

Although evidence has shown improved detection and outcome when primary care providers (PCP) screen for depression, adolescents are not routinely screened in the primary care setting (Cronholm, Barg, & Pailer et al., 2010; Sanders, 2006; Zenlea et al., 2014; Zuckerbrot, Maxon, & Pagar et al., 2007). Studies have shown that many of the nation's youth do not receive regular medical care (Bloom & Freeman, 2015). About one third of adolescents age 12 to 17 have not seen their PCP for more than six months and even if they present themselves to their PCP, few are screened for depression (Bloom & Freeman, 2015; McGoey, Huang, & Palmes, 2013; Zenlea et al., 2014). The data obtained from the National Ambulatory Medical Care Survey and the National Hospital

Ambulatory Care Survey showed an extremely low rate of 0.2% documented depression screenings during the 46,347 ambulatory care visits surveyed (Zenlea et al., 2014). There are many reasons for PCP not to screen for depression including lack of time, lack of referral resources, lack of knowledge and training, and limited reimbursement (Diamond et al., 2012; Sanders, 2006). Similarly, lack of time, high workload, lack of knowledge about screening, lack of a screening tool, and lack of resources for follow-up all contribute to low screening and referral rates in schools (Bohnenkamp, Stephan, & Bobo, 2015; Prymachuk, Graham, Haddad, & Tylee, 2012).

The Importance of Adolescent Depression Screening in Schools

Adolescence is an important developmental stage, characterized by a search for identity and a desire for acceptance by peers, and when a cascade of physical, intellectual, and psychological changes takes place. Young people who have difficulties accomplishing these developmental tasks are especially vulnerable to developing major depression. Literature shows the negative effect of depression on school attendance, academic performance, social well-being, and risky behaviors (McCarty, Wymbs, & Mason et al., 2013; Montag, Brodine, & Alcaraz et al., 2015; Riglin, Petrides, Frederickson, & Rice, 2014; Verboom, Sijtsema, Verhulst, Penninx, & Ormel, 2013). At-risk youths are more likely to suffer from MDE, anxiety disorder, substance abuse, and violence as they grow into adulthood (Bhatia & Bhatia, 2007; Merikangas, He, & Burstein, 2010). Longitudinal data reveals a significant correlation between future criminal behavior and adolescent depression (Anderson, Cesur, & Tekin, 2015). Depression not only has detrimental effects on the physical and mental health of the

individual but also adds significant impact on the economic and social burden of society. Therefore, early identification and treatment of depression in adolescents is vital.

Besides home, adolescents spent most of their time at school. As the health experts in schools, school nurses are valuable advisers for students in dealing with their physical and emotional health needs. The National Association of School Nurses (NASN) emphasizes the unique position of the school nurse as a leader in coordinating school mental health services (NASN, 2013). School-based screening programs are feasible and effective in the early identification of depression in adolescents (Allison, Nativio, Mitchell, Ren, & Yuhasz, 2014; Carnevale, 2011; Carnevale, 2012).

Depression screening by school nurses can be done universally for all adolescent students at the school level or district-wide, or as the need arises during day-to-day encounters. Universal screening is an effective way of identifying depressive symptoms for early treatment but remains controversial due to student rights and privacy issues, anxiety, stigma, and unnecessary medication and treatment due to false positive screening results (Lehrman, 2006). Because of these reasons, universal screening has not been widely adopted in public schools. Need-based screening, on the other hand, focuses on students who present themselves to the health office or who are referred by teachers or other school personnel. With proper policy and procedure in place, school nurses can determine whether incorporating depression screening in their comprehensive health program is feasible and beneficial based on their own resources and circumstances. By improving understanding and awareness of adolescent depression and learning how to use a validated depression screening tool, school nurses will be better equipped to identify and refer students in need.

Depression Screening Education

In a survey conducted by the NASN, 33.3% of the 8,006 school nurses listed mental health as their top educational need (Mangena & Maughan, 2015). In order to provide the necessary training for school nurses to promote a change of practice, school health credential program should enrich their curriculum with updated content on screening and management of common adolescent mental health conditions. Professional continuing education programs, both in-person and web-based, can be developed to fill the gap of this educational need. An online adolescent depression screening education module was developed to help school nurses understand the importance to screen for depression in adolescent population and to provide them with an evidence based depression screening tool to identify and refer young people in distress. This module is accessible at <https://sites.google.com/view/depressionscreeningtraining>.

Over half of the school nurses surveyed by NASN prefer self-paced web based training for continuing education (Maughan & Mangena, 2014). The online education module provides easy access to depression screening training materials and professional resources at the convenience of the school nurses via desktop computer, tablets, or any mobile devices. The author also took into consideration different learning styles in order to engage the learners using the Visual, Aural, Read/Write, Kinesthetic sensory (VARK) modalities (Fleming & Mills, 1992; VARK Learn Limited, 2017). The education module utilizes a video presentation with colorful graphics and charts which is attractive to the visual learners. A professional voice over alongside the video presentation can engage the aural learners. The availability of handouts, bulleted slides, and the resource list is important for the reading and writing learners' needs. The case study at the end of the

presentation allows the kinesthetic learners to apply the newly acquired knowledge in a practical way.

The content of the module includes epidemiology, signs and symptoms, and diagnostic criteria of depression in adolescents, the role of school nurses in depression screening, and how to use the PHQ9 as a screening test. The case study guides the participant through the entire process of screening, communicating findings, and assisting the student and family with referral. The education module also includes hyperlinks to download the screening survey in English and in other languages, printable sample referral forms, the referral algorithm, and to websites of many professional mental health organizations. School nurses can easily access and print information for the student and the family whenever they need.

Depression Screening with the PHQ-9 Survey

To facilitate the screening process, the ideal tool needs to be easy to use, free or low cost, and require short administration and scoring time. The PHQ-9 is a nine-item self-reported survey, used to identify depressive symptoms and suicidal risk, that is available free of charge in the public domain, is easy to administer, and takes about a minute to complete (Table 1). The PHQ-9 has been validated in primary care settings for detecting clinical depression in adolescents with a sensitivity of 89.5% and specificity of 77.5% at a cutoff score of 11 (Richardson et al., 2010). Although, psychometrics at various cutoff scores yields different sensitivity and specificity, it is agreed by most experts that the PHQ-9 is a valid and reliable tool for adolescent screening (Allgaier, Pietsch, Fruhe, Sigl-Glockner, & Schulte-Korne, 2012; Ganguly et al., 2013; Johnson, Harris, Spitzer, & Williams (2002); Richardson et al., 2010; Tsai et al., 2014). Scoring

and interpreting the PHQ-9 is relatively simple and straightforward. The higher the score the more severe the depression episode.

Table 1

Advantages of PHQ-9

-
- Takes a minute to complete
 - Easy to administer, score, and interpret
 - Free in the Public Domain
 - Widely used in Primary Care Setting
 - Available in many languages
-

Referral and Follow-Up

Students who score < 10 are probably not depressed or only mildly depressed. These students should be observed with “check-ins” as needed. Students with a score equal to or greater than 10 are considered moderately to severely depressed and should be referred for professional care and have regular follow-up in short intervals (Figure 2). The school nurse should discuss the screening results with parents’ either in-person or by phone and make appropriate referrals for mental health services. It is important to obtain a signed release of medical information so the school nurse can discuss treatment plans with the physician or mental health provider. In addition to outside providers, the school nurse should also make a referral to the school counselor or school psychologist, if such resources are available, for school-based mental health services. A Student Success, or similar school-based team, referral is often necessary when the depressed student shows poor academic performance or presents with significant behavioral concerns. Finally, it

is important to keep in mind that if a student responds to item nine on the PHQ-9, that he or she has contemplated self-harm and is suicidal, the school nurse should immediately notify the principal and the district Crisis Intervention Team. In these cases, the student should be referred for immediate treatment according to district protocol.

Figure 2. Referral algorithm based on PHQ-9 score.

Implications for School Nursing Practice

The NASN (2013), in its position statement on mental health in students, emphasized the vital role of school nurses in “identifying students struggling with mental, psychosocial or emotional issues, which, when not recognized, may affect educational

achievement and development of full academic potential” (para. 14). Indeed, the ultimate goal of school nursing practice is to help students reach their full academic potential through an array of activities that promote health and prevent disease. Therefore, it is imperative that school nurses understand the detrimental effects of depression on the physical, emotional and social well-being, and academic performance of students.

With a serious shortage in mental health providers and low reimbursement rate, there has been a trend to shift mental health services into the primary care and school settings. The Mental Health in Schools Act [H.R. 1211] (2015) was introduced to provide federal funding for comprehensive school-based mental health programs and improve the link between the schools and community mental health agencies. The role of school nurses in school-based mental health service is imperative. In addition to being expert in assessment and referral, the school nurse plays an important role in the coordination of care to facilitate communication and collaboration between student and family, school teachers and counselors, health care providers, third party payors, and community agencies so that the comprehensive health needs of the student can be met (McClanahan & Weismuller, 2014). It is best practice for school nurses to keep a current and periodically updated list of local mental health providers and agencies for referral to ensure students are able to obtain the care they need. A student with severe depression and significant academic difficulty may be eligible for educational services and school counseling services under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) or Section 504. In such a case, the school nurse needs to work with the student, family, and school personnel to develop an individualized education program with specialized instruction or counseling services so that the student can reach his or her academic goals.

Every school district should establish clear policies and procedures regarding mental health screening based on the needs of its student population, availability of resources, and the recommendation of school mental health professionals. School nurses should be actively involved in district wellness and mental health policymaking. As health experts in the education setting, school nurses can provide valuable input and recommendations surrounding how to best serve and advocate for adolescent students with depression and their families. It is important that the school nurse reviews, updates, and revises health policies periodically so that these policies reflect current evidence-based practice guidelines, and ensures confidentiality and compliance while caring for depressed students.

Conclusion

Adolescent depression is a silent epidemic in society and the consequences of untreated depression can be devastating. School nurses, being the most accessible health care provider in the school setting, are best positioned to help bridge the mental health service gap for students. It is important that school nurses are trained to recognize and screen for adolescent depression. An online education module on adolescent depression screening developed for school nurses is a cost-effective way to deliver this essential training. By increasing the knowledge of adolescent depression, knowing how to conduct evidence based screening and manage depressed students in the school setting, school nurses will be able to assist the students and their families to obtain the care they need.

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APPENDIX I

PERMISSION TO USE THE PRECEDE- PROCEED FRAMEWORK

RE: Request for Permission to use the PRECEDE-PROCEED Model - rachel.law@csu.fullerton.edu - Cal State Fullerton ...

https://mail.google.com/mail/u/0/?ui=2&view=bt&ver=w3296ks0xkrb&q=Larry.Green%40ucsf.edu&q=qs=true&search=qu

Move to Inbox

RE: Request for Permission to use the PRECEDE-PROCEED Model Inbox x

Green, Lawrence (Cancer Center) <Larry.Green@ucsf.edu> May 2 ☆ ↶ ⌵
 to me, mkreuter122, sn2006sj

Dear Ms Law,
 Thank you for your thoughtful request. You certainly have my permission, and I have permission from my co-author to respond similarly for him on such requests. I trust you have the 4th edition of our textbook on the model (Green & Kreuter, Health Program Planning: An Educational and Ecological Approach. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2005). You might also find helpful the bibliography we have compiled over the years since the first edition in 1980 and earlier articles formulating and testing the model since 1974. It is a searchable bibliography with links to abstracts and some full-texts of articles that have presented published accounts of other applications of the model in over 1000 publications.
 Today is the last day I'll be using this address, as I move into my professorial retirement from UCSF, but you can reach me at LWGreen@comcast.net if you need help beyond the text and bibliography, I can be reached at LWGreen@comcast.net. Seena Nair is listed above, if you need any help with your use of the website.

From: WanChing Rachel Law [rachel.law@csu.fullerton.edu]
Sent: Wednesday, April 27, 2016 3:08 PM
To: Green, Lawrence (Cancer Center)
Subject: Request for Permission to use the PRECEDE-PROCEED Model

Hi Dr. Green.

My name is Rachel Law. I am a family nurse practitioner and a graduate student at the Southern California CSU Doctor of Nursing Practice Consortium. I am working on a capstone project aiming to develop an education module for school nurses on adolescent depression screening. I would like to ask your permission to use your PRECEDE- PROCEED model as a framework to guide the development of the module.

My project will include literature review on the epidemiology of adolescent depression, the negative impacts of depression on adolescent physical and psychosocial well being, attendance, and academic productivity, the need for early identification and treatment, and the barriers to screening as perceived by the school nurses. I proposed to use PHQ-9 as a screening tool to help identify and refer students who present with signs of depression so that early intervention is possible. My goal is to create an online education module for school nurses to increase their awareness on adolescent depression and teach them how to use the PHQ-9 as a screening tool.

Thank you for your time reading my request. I look forward to hearing from you.

Sincerely,
 Rachel Law

...

APPENDIX K

PERMISSION TO USE VIDEO FROM AMERICAN FOUNDATION OF
SUICIDE PREVENTION

RE: Cal State Fullerton

Inbox x

Shelby Rowe <SRowe@afsp.org>

Jan 24

to Jessica, me, Traute ▾

Rachel, thank you for reaching out. Yes, you are more than welcome to use the More Than Sad videos as part of a training module for school nurses. You may upload the videos to an internal training site but not a site available to the general public.

Please let me know if you have any other questions.

All the Best!

Shelby Rowe, MBA
Manager of Education and Prevention Programs
American Foundation for Suicide Prevention
120 Wall Street | 29th floor | New York, NY 10005
srowe@afsp.org
T: [212.363.3500](tel:212.363.3500) ext. 2041